

ON CERTAIN KETO-SULPHONES

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Certain keto-sulphones have been prepared and their properties studied.

Search for simple sulphones was undertaken in this laboratory since 1945 (cf. Sikdar and Basu, this *Journal*, 1945, 22, 343; Sikdar, *ibid.*, 1946, 23, 203; Basu and Chandran, *Science & Culture*, 1949, 15, 34) in the belief that they may exert a chemotherapeutic action against pulmonary tuberculosis (cf. Bambas, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 668, 671). Many natural antibiotics again contain an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketonic chain (cf. Basu, *Science & Culture*, 1948, 14, 191); and Rinderknecht *et al.* (*Biochem. J.*, 1948, 41, 191) have made a systematic study on the nature of such chains and their relative activity against various pathogenic organisms. It is known that an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone readily reacts with benzenesulphinic acid (Kohler and Reimer, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1904, 31, 163). Accordingly it was considered to be of interest to find out the activity of 4-aminophenylsulphones that might be easily obtained by condensing *p*-aminobenzenesulphinic acid with $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketones. While the work was just in progress we came across a patent literature (Ind. Pat., 33544) where certain keto-sulphones were described. They are being found to be active against coliform organisms. As our intention was to work on some products that might be effective against *M. tuberculosis*, some unsaturated ketones containing salicylidene, cinnamylidene group, and similar other aromatic aldehydes were obtained by condensing the aldehydes with appropriate ketone and the resulting unsaturated ketones were condensed with *p*-acetylaminobenzenesulphinic acid, and in certain cases with free *p*-aminobenzenesulphinic acid. In general, it is difficult to isolate the latter condensation products directly by hydrolysing the reaction products between the unsaturated ketones and the *p*-acetylaminobenzenesulphinic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

General Method of Preparation.—*p*-Acetaminobenzenesulphinic acid (1 mol.) was refluxed with the respective unsaturated compound (1 mol.) in alcoholic medium for 1-2 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled when the crystals separated which were filtered off, washed and recrystallised from alcohol. In the case of compound (V), chloroform-alcohol mixture was used for recrystallisation. The compounds that have been prepared and studied are listed in Table I.

The acetyl compound, when refluxed with 25 c.c. of caustic soda solution (10%) for two hours, underwent hydrolysis, but it was difficult to isolate the free compounds in good and pure quality. The free compounds, *para*-aminophenylsulphone derivatives were, however, prepared by refluxing molar amounts of *p*-aminobenzenesulphinic acid and the corresponding $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketones for 2 to 5 hours in alcoholic solution. On cooling, crystals separated out and they were recrystallised from alcohol. The detailed characteristics are recorded in Table II.

TABLE I

No.	Compound.	General appearance and melting point.	Formula and M. W.	Percentage nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.
I.	R.CH[C ₆ H ₄ .OH(o)]CH ₂ CO.Me <i>p</i> -Acetaminophenyl (1- <i>o</i> -hydroxyphenyl-2-acetylethyl) sulphone.	White crystals, m.p. 173-74°	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₃ NS (361)	4.34	3.88
II.	R.CH[C ₆ H ₄ .OH(p)]CH ₂ CO.Me <i>p</i> -Acetaminophenyl (1- <i>p</i> -hydroxyphenyl-2-acetylethyl) sulphone.	White crystals, m.p. 152°	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₃ NS (361)	3.89	3.88
III.	R.CH[C ₆ H ₄ .OMe(p)]CH ₂ CO.Me <i>p</i> -Acetaminophenyl (1- <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl-2-acetylethyl) sulphone.	White needles, m.p. 150°	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₃ NS (375)	3.97	3.73
IV.	R.CH.CH ₂ CO.Me CH = CHPh <i>p</i> -Acetaminophenyl (1-styryl-2-acetylethyl) sulphone.	Brown crystals, m.p. 170° (decomp.)	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₃ NS (371)	3.27	3.77
V.	R.CH[C ₆ H ₄ .OH(o)]CH ₂ COPh <i>p</i> -Acetaminophenyl (1- <i>o</i> -hydroxyphenyl-2-benzoylethyl) sulphone.	White prisms, m.p. 133-34°	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₃ NS (423)	3.25	3.30
VI.	R.CH[C ₆ H ₄ .OH(p)]CH ₂ COPh <i>p</i> -Acetaminophenyl (1- <i>p</i> -hydroxyphenyl-2-benzoylethyl) sulphone.	White plates, m.p. 192-93° (decomp.)	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₃ NS (423)	3.70	3.30
VII.	R.CH[C ₆ H ₄ .OMe(p)]CH ₂ COPh <i>p</i> -Acetaminophenyl (1- <i>p</i> -methoxy-2-benzoylethyl) sulphone.	White crystals, m.p. 177-78° (decomp.)	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₃ NS (437)	2.86	3.20
VIII.	R.CH.CH ₂ COPh CH = CH.Ph <i>p</i> -Acetaminophenyl (1-styryl-2-benzoylethyl) sulphone.	White shining plates, m.p. 164°	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₃ NS (433)	2.86	3.23
IX.	R.CH[C ₆ H ₄ Br.OH(m)]CH ₂ CO.Me <i>p</i> -Acetaminophenyl (1:2'-hydroxy-5'-bromophenyl-2-acetylethyl) sulphone.	Pale yellow crystals, m.p. 174°	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₃ NSBr (440)	2.87	3.18
X.	R.CH[C ₆ H ₄ .OH(o)]CH ₂ CO.CH = CH.C ₆ H ₄ OH <i>p</i> -Acetaminophenyl (1- <i>o</i> -hydroxyphenyl-2-β- <i>o</i> -hydroxyphenylacroylethyl) sulphone.	Reddish brown crystals, m.p. 170-71°	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₃ NS (455)	3.29	3.01
XI.	 <i>p</i> -Acetaminophenyl (3:4-dihydrocoumaryl) sulphone.	White plates, m.p. 213-214°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₃ NS (345)	3.89	4.06

TABLE II

R = NH₂.C₆H₄.SO₂—

No.	Compounds	General appearance and melting point.	Formula and M. W.	Percentage nitrogen	
				Found.	Calc.
II. a	R.CH[C ₆ H ₄ .OH(<i>p</i>)]CH ₂ .CO.CH ₃ <i>p</i> -Aminophenyl (1- <i>p</i> -hydroxyphenyl-2-acetyl ethyl) sulphone.	White crystals, decomposes at 106-97°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₄ NS (319)	4.12	4.39
III. a	R.CH[C ₆ H ₄ .OMe(<i>p</i>)]CH ₂ .CO.CH ₃ <i>p</i> -Aminophenyl (1- <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl-2-acetyl ethyl) sulphone.	White crystals, m.p. 142-43° (decomp.)	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₄ NS (333)	3.91	4.20
VI. a	R.CH[C ₆ H ₄ .OH(<i>p</i>)]CH ₂ .COPh <i>p</i> -Aminophenyl (1- <i>p</i> -hydroxyphenyl-2-benzoyl ethyl) sulphone.	Pale yellow needles, m.p. 182-83° (decomp.)	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₄ NS (387)	3.41	3.67
VII. a	R.CH[C ₆ H ₄ .OMe(<i>p</i>)]CH ₂ .COPh <i>p</i> -Aminophenyl (1- <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl-2-benzoyl ethyl) sulphone.	White prisms, m.p. 166-67°	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₄ NS (395)	3.32	3.54
VIII. a	R.CH.CH ₂ .COPh CH=CHPh <i>p</i> -Aminophenyl (1-styryl-2-benzoyl ethyl) sulphone.	Pale yellow crystals, m.p. 194-95°	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ O ₃ NS (391)	3.95	3.58
X. a	R.CH[C ₆ H ₄ .OH(<i>o</i>)]CH ₂ .CO.CH=CH. C ₆ H ₄ .OH(<i>o</i>) <i>p</i> -Aminophenyl[(1- <i>o</i> -hydroxyphenyl) 2(<i>β</i> - <i>o</i> -hydroxyphenylacroyl ethyl)-sulphone.	Dark red crystals, decomposes at 214-215°	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₆ NS (423)	3.49	3.31

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